

Visible Light Photocatalytic Activity of ZnO-TiO₂ Composites for the Degradation of Rhodamine B

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Abstract

High quality ZnO doped Titanium dioxide nanoplatelets were synthesized by hydrothermal method. Titanium dioxide plays an important role in Solar cells applications. Due to absorb the low-energy radiation, it tunes the optical property of Titanium dioxide. Composition, structure and morphology of the samples were analyzed. Characterization studies were done by X-ray diffraction and it clearly confirm the hexagonal wurtzite structure with same lattice constants; $a=3.248\text{Å}$ and $c=5.212\text{Å}$. It reveals the doped samples are improved without affecting the parent lattice. The morphological and optical properties of Zinc and Titanium oxide materials were studied by Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and UV-vis spectroscopy. The Photocatalytic degradation of Rhodamine B dye under visible light radiation were studied by using different experimental condition in initial dye concentration and rate constant was calculated using L-H model.

Keywords: Composite materials, Colloidal processing, TiO₂ and ZnO

References

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